

EFFECTS OF LAMINATION ON CRITICAL PLY FAILURE IN COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

A knowledge of the compressive properties of fiber composite laminates is of much interest as composites are used in strength critical applications. Compressive strength has been difficult to measure as it apparently depends on a number of variables that are not well understood. In the present investigation, axially loaded tubular specimens were used to determine the compressive properties of three different laminates, using three different carbon fiber/epoxy material systems. The results show that the strain to failure in the axial plies depends on the total laminate layup. This result has also been reported elsewhere in the literature as well.

1. INTRODUCTION

The compressive failure properties of laminates are of increasing interest in structural applications of fiber composites. Interest in the strength properties of composites is increasing as strength-critical applications are developed, in addition to those that depend primarily on stiffness properties. As practical structures are typically made with multiple fiber orientations, either as laminates or as filament wound structures, for example, it is necessary to be able to predict failure under these general conditions. Despite the importance of the compressive strength properties of laminates, there is not at present a well established theoretical and/or experimental basis for the prediction of ultimate strength in compression.

Failure properties of laminates under conditions of biaxial tension-tension and tension-compression stress states have been investigated in our laboratory. This work has established that failure of fiber dominated laminates can be predicted on the basis of fiber failure in a

critical ply, and that fiber failure can be based on the maximum fiber direction normal strain criterion. These results appear to hold over a wide variety of states of stress, laminate layups, and carbon fiber systems [1-3], and references contained within. In view of the success of this critical ply criterion for tension stress states, we have recently investigated the applicability of the above procedure for uniaxial, biaxial, and triaxial compression stress states. The results appear to show that the failure properties of the critical ply are not independent of the states of stress and the layup, but rather depend on both of these variables. Thus we have termed the apparent strength of the critical ply in compression an "in-situ" property [4]. Further evidence of this behavior will be presented in this paper. A dependence of strain at failure in compression on the layup has also been observed by Sohi, Hahn, and Williams [5].

In general compression tests of fiber composite materials have been somewhat difficult to perform [6-10]. Overall stability of the specimen must be ensured to prevent buckling. This has often been achieved by either using short gage length specimens, or adding side supports of various types such as a honeycomb core. Either method introduces uncertainties. While careful attention to detail can insure reproducibility of results for a given type of test [6], comparison between different types of tests can reveal differences approaching a factor of 1.5 or more [11]. As a further complication, it has been reported that compressive strength varies with lateral confining pressure [12,13] and thus presumably with the state of stress. It is known, for example, in materials such as concrete or rock that this state of stress effect can give higher apparent strength values in short gage length specimens because of transverse compressive stresses introduced by end effects.

In an effort to shed new light on some of the experimental uncertainties, we have employed a tubular specimen loaded in axial compression. The cylindrical specimen resists buckling by virtue of its shape, although the wall thickness must be sufficient to avoid shell buckling. The specimen thus avoids the short gage length problems.

In the following, the results of experiments on axial compression of tubular specimens made from carbon/epoxy laminates will be examined. In particular, the dependence of the apparent failure properties of the critical plies on the layup will be pointed out. The results of a micro-buckling model will be compared with the data, to give insight into the failure mechanisms involved.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The tubular specimen employed is shown in Fig 1. Finite element analyses of a similar specimen have been reported in [14]. The experimental results support the analysis in that failures are usually

found within the gage section and not at the ends of the specimens. Failure values for specimens that fail near the end grips are not significantly lower than those that fail in the gage section. The analysis also indicates that no significant variations of strain through the thickness exist for axial loading of the cylinders.

Table 1 gives a summary of the materials and laminate layups tested. The laminates used were a predominantly axial fiber [90/06/90/06/90]_t, an axially biased [(0₂/±45)₂]S layup, and the quasi-isotropic [(0/90/±45)₂]S layup. The materials used were AS4/3501-6, IM7/8551-7, and Graphil 33-500/YLA 135-1, all carbon fiber/epoxy systems. The specimens were all manufactured by applying prepreg tape to an aluminum mandrel. It is necessary to have some fibers with a component of the fiber direction in the hoop direction, to eliminate problems in removing the specimen from the mandrel. As a consequence, a specimen with a purely axial layup cannot be manufactured using present techniques. Details of the manufacturing process are given in [4].

3. RESULTS

Typical response curves are given in Figs 2 and 3 for AS4/3501-6 and IM78551-7 laminates. These readings are from three axial and three hoop strain gages located at the axial midplane and spaced equally around the circumference of the specimens. The figures show the moderate amount of scatter between the three gages, which is typical of all of the tests. However some gage failures occurred at strains close to failure. It is important to note that no divergence of the gage readings is seen that would be a signal that specimen buckling is occurring. It is thus concluded that the specimens were of adequate thickness to prevent buckling failures.

A plot of the axial stress-strain response for three layups of IM7/8551-7 is shown in Fig 4. In this plot the stress is the average axial stress for the laminate, and the strain is the average of the three axial strain gages. It can be seen that the stress-strain response differs with lamination type as would be expected, with the laminates with the higher percentage of axial fibers showing a stiffer response. A comparison is also given with the stiffness predicted by classical lamination theory for each layup. It can be seen that the results are in good agreement with lamination theory as would be expected, but all of the specimens exhibit some softening at the higher stress levels. It should be noted that the failure strain varies significantly between the laminates for all of the materials. A plot of the average compressive failure strain is given in Fig 5 for the three laminate types and three carbon fiber material systems. It can be seen that all three material systems show a similar dependence of the compressive failure strain on the laminate layup.

4. DISCUSSION

The major point of the present work is to document the fact that the compression failure properties of the critical axial plies in a laminate are not independent of the laminate layup, but instead apparently depend on the layup. As mentioned above, this behavior has been previously reported by Sohi, Hahn, and Williams [5], but it is significant that it is also seen in the present results using a different experimental specimen and different material systems. The present results are similar to that reported in [4] using a single material system.

As mentioned above, one of the experimental problems that must be addressed in compression tests is that of specimen buckling. In the present experiments with tubular specimens, it is believed that specimen buckling did not occur. The main evidence is the uniformity of the strain gage readings. If buckling did occur, it is believed that it would have shown up in a divergence of the readings from the strain gages spaced around the circumference of the specimens. Additionally, no visual evidence of buckling was observed. The R/t (radius/thickness) ratio used in these specimens was approximately 10. It is believed that this R/t ratio is appropriate to prevent buckling. However it does introduce the possibility that stress or strain variations could occur through the wall thickness. As mentioned above, however, finite element analyses showed that this effect was not significant [14].

A micro-buckling model has been developed that attempts to explain the dependence of compressive failure strain on laminate layup [15]. The model is based on an assumption of buckling of individual fibers in the critical axial plies. The fibers are assumed to have initial eccentricities in an idealized sinusoidal manner. The model is based on a "beam-column on elastic foundation" equation, much like the development given by Hahn and Williams [16], with an individual fiber being the beam-column, and the matrix being the elastic foundation that provides support to the fiber. The novel feature of the model of [15] is that it incorporates the stiffness of the adjacent layers of the laminate into the analysis. The assumption is that the non-buckling layers of the laminate that are adjacent to the critical compression ply that is undergoing microbuckling deformations tend to stabilize the critical ply, by virtue of the through-the-thickness shear stresses that are required from conditions of compatibility. As a consequence, two patterns of shear stress distributions act to stabilize the axial fibers. These are the in-plane shears based on resistance of the matrix to the buckling deformation, and through-the-thickness shears that result from the assumption that while the the axial fiber buckles, the adjacent plies do not.

A consequence of using a model that includes initial imperfections is that the limiting case is no longer bifurcation buckling, but rather continuously increasing deformations. Limits to this deformation must be based on the physical processes involved. In the model of [15], three limiting conditions were used. These were failure of the fibers in compression, failure of the fibers in tension (obtained due to the bending associated with the microbuckling), and failure of the interface bond between fiber and matrix. Under many conditions the interface bond appears to be the limiting factor. Thus compression failure is predicted to depend on both the matrix shear stiffness and the interface shear strength.

A typical comparison of the model with experimental data is shown in Fig 6, taken from [15]. The model displays the experimentally observed dependence of the failure strain on the overall laminate layup, expressed here in terms of the inplane shear modulus of the nonbuckling portion of the laminate. It can be seen that reasonable agreement with the main trend of the data is observed. It should be pointed out however, that the initial eccentricity of the fibers was not directly measured, but was treated as a free parameter in the model and determined by fitting to the data for the predominantly axial ply laminate. The same value of eccentricity was then used for the other laminates as well. While the model necessarily includes a number of simplifying assumptions, it does at least provide a plausible explanation for the dependence of the compression failure strains on the overall laminate layup.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

An investigation has been carried out to determine the compressive strength properties of three different laminates and three carbon/epoxy materials using tubular specimens. The laminates used were a predominantly axial fiber $[90/0_6/90/0_6/90]_t$, an axially biased $[(0_2/\pm 45)_2]_S$ layup, and the quasi-isotropic $[(0/90/\pm 45)_2]_S$ layup. The materials used were AS4/3501-6, IM7/8551-7, and Graphil 33-500/YLA 135-1, all carbon fiber/epoxy systems. The stress-strain and failure properties were measured. The results show that the compressive failure strain in the axial plies depends on the laminate layup.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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Table 1. Materials and Layups Tested

Materials:	AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy IM7/8551-7 carbon/epoxy Graphil 33-500/YLA 135-1 carbon/epoxy
Layups:	[90/06/90/06/90] _t [(0 ₂ /±45) ₂] _S [(0/90/±45) ₂] _S

Fig 1. Schematic diagram of cylindrical axial compression specimen.

Fig 2. Stress-strain response in axial compression of AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy in $[(0_2/\pm 45)_2]_S$ laminate. Three axial and three hoop strain gages shown.

Fig 3. Stress-strain response in axial compression of IM7/8551-7 carbon/epoxy in $[(0_2/\pm 45)_2]_S$ laminate. Three axial and three hoop strain gages shown.

Fig 4. Average axial stress-strain response in uniaxial compression of IM7/8551-7 carbon/epoxy. Laminates are given in Table 1.

Fig 5. Comparison of average failure strains for three carbon/epoxy materials and three laminates.

Fig 6. Comparison of model prediction for compressive failure strain with experimental data for AS4/3501-6 laminates, from [15].